

TESTS TO MEASURE THE MATERIAL PROPERTIES RELEVANT TO THE MODELLING OF PROCESS INDUCED DEFORMATIONS IN COMPOSITE PARTS

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SUMMARY: Modelling of the manufacturing deformations in composite parts has attracted considerable research effort in recent years. The motivation behind this effort is to have a reliable analytical method to predict the deformations in order to make necessary tool corrections to obtain the dimensional fidelity required by aerospace industry. The reliability of the predictive methods highly depends on the reliability of the material data used in modelling. This paper summarizes the state of the current experimental research to measure some of the material properties relevant to the modelling of composites processing. The mechanisms that are effective during various stages of the Manufacturer's Recommended Cure Cycle are discussed. Cure kinetics of the resin, points of gelation and vitrification, cure shrinkage behaviour, modulus development by cure, and coefficient of thermal expansion in the transverse direction for a carbon fibre thermosetting composite are investigated experimentally.

KEYWORDS: Thermoset composites, cure shrinkage, residual stress, Dynamic Mechanical Analysis, Differential Scanning Calorimetry

INTRODUCTION

Composite parts with curved geometry or a bend radius spring-in as they come out of the mould. The amount of angle closure is reported to depend on several variables: lay-up orientation, part thickness and shape, tool material and cure cycle [1-4]. Since tool correction by trial and error is an expensive and time consuming task, the development of an analytical tool to predict the spring-in taking into account various factors has also attracted a considerable research effort [5-9].

Another important mechanism that is the focus of some current research effort [10-16] is the friction between the tool and the part, and this mechanism can have a major influence on the final geometry of flat sections if the coefficients of thermal expansion of the tool and the part are different. Tool interaction causes the stretching of the low shear modulus, curing composite and results in in-plane residual stresses with through-the-thickness gradients that cause distortion.

However, the predictive methods are reliable only if accurate data about the behaviour of the material in question is available, and the model reflects most of the important phenomena that take place during the Manufacturer's Recommended Cure Cycle (MRCC).

In this paper, the behaviour of a thermosetting composite is investigated experimentally, and guide rules for a sound modelling of the material's response to the imposed cured cycle are tried to be extracted. Some tests are proposed to measure the gel point, vitrification point, as

well as the development of the degree of cure, the glass transition temperature, the resin shrinkage strains, modulus development, and frictional stresses between two prepreg layers and between a tooling material and the composite as a function of MRCC. This experimental approach to decipher the composite's response to the MRCC is believed to be more accurate and reliable and involves fewer assumptions as compared to semi-analytical approaches based on micromechanics theory that predicts the composite's response from the response of constituent materials.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material and the Manufacturer's Recommended Cure Cycle (MRCC)

The prepreg used in this study is a unidirectional carbon/epoxy, produced by Hexcel Composites with a designation of AS4/8552. The nominal thickness of the prepreg was given as 0.250 mm. The MRCC consists of a first ramp of 2°C/min up to 120 °C and a first hold at 120 °C for 60 min, a second ramp of 2°C/min up to 180 °C and a second hold at 180 °C for 120 min. A pressure of 0.7 MPa is applied throughout the cycle.

The Development of the Degree of Cure and the Glass Transition Temperature

The development of the degree of cure, α , during the manufacturing cycle is modelled using the cure kinetics model proposed by Cole et al. [17], which takes into account a shift from kinetics to diffusion control:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{K\alpha^m(1-\alpha)^n}{1 + e^{\frac{C[\alpha-\alpha_c]}}}; \alpha_c = \alpha_{c0} + \alpha_{cT}T; K = Ae^{(-\Delta E/RT)} \quad (1)$$

where ΔE is the activation energy, A is the pre-exponential cure rate coefficient, m and n are first and second exponential constants, C is the diffusion constant, α_{c0} is the critical degree of cure at $T=0$ K, and α_{cT} is the constant accounting for the increase in critical resin degree of cure with temperature. The constants of the model are calculated by using dynamic DSC tests in a previous study [18]. The MRCC was simulated in DSC for both prepreg and the neat resin, and no difference is found between the two. The values of the constants are given in Table 1.

In order to determine the development of the degree of cure and the glass transition temperature, T_g , resin samples squeezed out of specimens quenched at various stages of cure during the MRCC were also tested by DSC.

In Fig. 1, the process temperature, T , the glass transition temperature, T_g , calculated using Eq.2, and α predicted by the cure kinetics model are plotted versus time throughout the MRCC, together with the DSC measurements of α and T_g for cure quenched samples. There is excellent agreement between the model predictions and the experimental measurements. From the graph it can be seen that the time of vitrification occurs 45 minutes after the 180°C soak period.

Table 1: Cure kinetics constants for 8552 resin

Constant	Value	Unit	Comments
H_u	6.5×10^4	J/g	Ultimate heat of reaction
E_a	7.0×10^4	J/gmol	Activation energy
A	0.5	s^{-1}	Cure rate coefficient
m	1.5		First exponential constant
n	8.314		Second exponential constant
R	30	J/mol/K	Gas constant
C	5.171×10^{-3}		Diffusion constant
α_{CT}	-1.515		Constant accounting for increase in ultimate α with T
α_{c0}	6.5×10^4		Critical degree of cure at T=0K

Figure 1: Cure kinetics model predictions for degree of cure plotted versus time throughout the MRCC. The degree of cure and T_g measurements of quenched samples are superimposed.

Gel Point and the Frictional Stresses Between the Tool and the Composite

A novel technique was developed in a previous study [19] to investigate the frictional processes during composite manufacturing. The test equipment consists of two heating plates and a set of 4 precise springs, which provided the pressure used in the MRCC. The test area is heated by a couple of stainless steel heaters, and a programmable temperature controller was used to control the temperature profiles.

The specimens used to investigate the frictional stresses between two prepregs were prepared by folding two 500x45 mm prepreg strips. The test area, where plies were overlapping each other, was 64 mm long. The specimen was held in the grips of a servo-hydraulic testing machine by two self-locking end tabs as shown in Fig. 2. The overlapping prepregs are pulled past each other at a constant rate in the servo-hydraulic testing machine as the MRCC is applied. In the specimen to investigate the frictional stresses between the tool and the prepreg, one of the prepregs is replaced by an aluminium plate which is 45 mm wide and 1 mm thick.

Figure 2: Ply pull-out set-up

Fig. 3 shows the shear stress versus time traces of prepreg/prepreg interfaces (Fig. 3.a) and tool/prepreg interfaces (Fig. 3.b) at a test rate of 0.10 mm/min. The results of two tests are shown at each plot. During the first test the actuator motion was continuous throughout the MRCC (Test C), and at the second test, the actuator motion was stopped during the hold periods (Test I) to replicate the fact that the relative motion at the interfaces stop during the hold periods since the temperature is constant and there is no tool expansion.

Figure 3: Inter-ply shear stresses (a) and tool interaction shear stresses (b) during the MRCC. In trace (C), the actuator movement is continuous, whereas in trace (I) it is interrupted during the hold periods.

The plot of shear stress between two prepreps as a function of time (Fig. 3.a) shows that as the temperature increases in the first ramp, the initial feature is a rapid rise to a peak stress. After a certain peak stress at around 30°C, the resin turn from a rubbery to a liquid state and from this point to about 60 °C, the shear stress falls as temperature increases. The shear stress is reduced by an order of magnitude between 30 °C and 60 °C, and passing from a minimum at about 60 °C, it starts to rise, although there is no cure development and the resin viscosity is expected to continue to fall due to increasing temperature. This feature is explained by an increase in the friction as a result of the fibre tows being intermingled while the lubrication effect of the resin is reduced. The shear stress keeps on increasing to an asymptotic value by the end of the first hold period at 120°C, suggesting that in this region the response appears not to be resin dominated, the viscoelastic effects seem to be suppressed and the shear stress is basically dominated by the interaction of fibre tows.

It can be observed that at the beginning of the second ramp, the shear stress reduces as the viscosity increases. However, due to acceleration in cross-linking of the resin, further increase

in temperature does not cause a further decrease in shear stress. After a certain point, the shear stress increases slightly up to a point around 160°C where a sharp increase in shear stress and linear shear stress-displacement behaviour is observed. The point at which there is a sharp increase in shear stress is the gel point, and this technique has proved to be very effective in determining the gel point of the resin, as defined as the point where a 3-D polymer network is formed so that the structure can bear significant applied stresses.

If the actuator movement is stopped at the 120°C and 180°C holds to replicate the ply movements during the MRCC better, there is considerable relaxation of shear stresses during the constant temperature holds, even at the later stages of the second hold.

The shear stress traces for the prepreg/tool interfaces, shown in Fig. 3.b follow a similar pattern to the prepreg/prepreg interfaces. The shear stress increases during the first ramp, reaching a peak around 60°C, decreases to a minimum as the temperature increases and viscosity decreases, increases towards the end of the first ramp due to increasing fibre friction between the tool and the prepreg. If the actuator movement is uninterrupted, the shear stress keeps on increasing, with a sharp rise at the gel point around 160°C during the second ramp. The prepreg is stuck to the tool until it separates from the tool at around the vitrification point, and after that point, the interface condition is a sliding friction condition with a constant shear stress. If the actuator movement is stopped during the hold periods, there is some relaxation in the shear stress; however this relaxation is not as dominant as the prepreg/prepreg interfaces.

The Development of Cure Shrinkage During the MRCC

Through-the-thickness cure shrinkage of AS4/8552 composite was measured using a novel technique in a previous study [20], and some of the results obtained in this study are summarized here. In this technique, unidirectional and crossply stacks of prepregs were placed in between two heating plates, and the whole assembly was placed in a die-set. The MRCC was replicated in terms of temperature and a pressure of 0.68 atm. (approximately 1/10 of the autoclave pressure). The through-thickness strain was measured using a non-contact video extensometer.

Strain versus time graphs for three unidirectional and cross-ply samples throughout the MRCC are plotted in Fig. 4.a and Fig. 4.b together with the recorded temperature profile. The initial preconsolidation levels were different for the three samples in each batch, as reflected by the different consolidation strains at the first ramp and first hold of the MRCC. In the same Figures, the strains are zeroed at the peak during second ramp so that the shrinkage after the gel point can be determined.

Several regions where different mechanisms are effective can be distinguished. At Region I the resin is expanding as a result of increasing temperature, however at about 60°C, the thickness starts to reduce due to consolidation, trapped air rejection and resin flow, which continues in Region II, up the onset of the second ramp. Cure kinetics indicate that there may be some cure shrinkage as well. However in Region III, in the first part of the second ramp, there are three mechanisms competing against each other: consolidation, cure shrinkage, and thermal expansion in liquid state, where the latter is believed to be dominant. The peak coincides with the onset of gelation, though that should be considered as a mere coincidence. In Region IV, the consolidation mechanism ceases to be effective; since the resin is gelled, there cannot be any void migration or resin flow. The cure shrinkage becomes dominant over thermal expansion and an overall reduction in thickness is recorded.

The total through-the-thickness strains after the onset of gelation is an important parameter in terms of residual stress modelling. The average values are found to be $0.48 \pm 0.06\%$ for unidirectional and $0.98 \pm 0.13\%$ for cross-ply composites. The through-the-thickness strain for

the cross-ply composite is approximately twice that of the unidirectional, indicating that there is no lateral constraint in unidirectional composites, whereas in crossply samples, the lateral contraction is completely constrained and only through-the-thickness contraction takes place.

Figure 4: Measured through-the-thickness strain as a function of time of a unidirectional stack (a) and a cross-ply stack (b) undergoing MRCC. The strains are zeroed at the peak during the second ramp.

Modulus Development during the MRCC

The modulus measurements are carried out in a TA Instruments Q800 Dynamic Mechanical Analyser (DMA) on preregs in transverse shear mode. Trials to start the DMA test at the beginning of the MRCC showed that the specimen can not be hold by the fixture since the resin in liquid state is flowing at early stages of curing. For this reason precuring of the specimen to the gelled state is necessary. Eight layers of prepreg with dimensions 50mmx50mm is precured in a hot press by applying a very light pressure and replicating the MRCC in terms of temperature. The process is stopped at 160°C, and at this state the resin is gelled and able to sustain mechanical loading in the transverse direction. The nominal thickness of the specimen is 2 mm, and 10mmx10mm specimens are cut from the precured prepreg.

The specimen is installed in the shear fixture in DMA as shown schematically in Fig. 5.a in such a way that the movement of the crosshead is in the direction perpendicular to the fibres. The temperature is raised to 160°C with a ramp of 10°C/min in order to avoid further curing before the point in the MRCC is reached. The heating rate is dropped to 2 °C/min as recommended by MRCC. MRCC is followed after the temperature reaches 160°C.

Stress relaxation experiments are carried out in the DMA testing machine as follows: The specimen is loaded with a constant strain rate of 0.005 rad/min up to 0.005 rad. and then the stress is allowed to relax to an asymptotic value and the relaxed shear modulus is recorded. This measurement procedure is repeated at every 10 min until the end of the second hold period at 180 °C. The relaxed shear modulus is believed to be the relevant material property for residual stress modelling, since the autoclave processes are slow enough to allow the build-up stresses to relax to a minimum value. The relaxation is observed to be completed within 1 min at each measurement.

The results are plotted in logarithmic scale in Fig. 5.b together with the MRCC. As can be seen in the figure, the modulus rises steadily in the rubbery phase and then increases two

orders of magnitude as the resin vitrifies. The modulus does not change considerably after vitrification.

Figure 5: Development of the transverse Young's modulus during MRCC

Coefficient of Thermal Expansion During Cooling

The thermal expansion coefficient (CTE) in the transverse direction was measured using high temperature strain gauges. Five strain gauges of gauge length 2 mm (Gauges 1-5) were bonded onto a plate of composite on a line in the transverse direction with 10 mm spacing between the centres of each gauge. In addition to those, two strain gauges of 50 mm gauge length (Gauges 6 and 7) were bonded on the opposite faces of the composite plate to observe if there is any bowing of the plate. Compensation gauges were bonded on a zero thermal expansion titanium silicate glass. The plate and the titanium silicate glass are heated to 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in an oven and then let to cool inside the oven. The strain gauges are balanced at 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the strain and temperatures on both the plate and the titanium silicate glass are recorded. Linear regression is performed on the individual curves, and the CTE values are obtained. The strain gauges of 2 mm gauge length exhibit a variability reflecting the point-to-point variation of the CTE values along the plate and the misalignment problems. The average value of these five strain gauges is $32.6 \pm 1.8 \mu\epsilon/^{\circ}\text{C}$ and this value matches very closely the values measured from 50 mm strain gauges (32.6 and 32.9 $\mu\epsilon/^{\circ}\text{C}$).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

By reviewing the data presented in this study, various stages of the curing process can be identified. During these different stages different set of mechanisms are effective, and different approaches should be adopted to model the curing process in order to predict the final manufacturing distortions locked in the part during processing. In Fig. 6, the MRCC is divided to various stages, and the mechanisms that are believed to be effective during these stages are listed in Table 2. During the first ramp (Stage I), consolidation, tool-part interaction and inter-ply slip are effective. This is an important finding, since it reflects the fact that considerable fibre stresses can develop during the early stages of the cure due to consolidation of the corner sections and tool interaction, and what percentage of these stresses are locked in depends on the relaxation attained by inter-ply slip.

Figure 6: Various stages of the MRCC

Table 2 Mechanisms that are effective during various stages of the MRCC

Mechanism	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
Consolidation	#	#					
Inter-ply Slip	#	#	#				
Tool Interaction	#		#	#			
Relaxation		#			#		
Thermal Expansion	#		#	#			
Cure Shrinkage			#	#	#		
Modulus Development				#	#		
Thermal Contraction							#

During the first hold at 120°C (Stage II), consolidation continues, as the stresses due to consolidation and tool-part interaction relax to a certain extent. During the second ramp up to the gel point (Stage III), the resin expands as the consolidation ceases, and thermal expansion and cure shrinkage compete with each other, and since the CTE of the tool is usually higher than the composite, tool interaction stresses built-up.

During the second part of the second ramp after gel point, tool interaction is still effective, whereas inter-ply slip ceases as a result of inter-ply locking after gelation. During this stage, cure shrinkage overtakes thermal expansion.

During Stages IV and V, the modulus of the composite develops, and the transverse stresses can only be locked-in when the resin is capable of sustaining mechanical loads. The magnitude of the locked in stresses are determined by the amount of cure shrinkage, as well as the constraints imposed on free shrinkage, and the history of resin modulus development during the MRCC with respect to the history of cure shrinkage.

At stage VI, there is not any effective mechanism to be considered for a modelling effort. Stage VII is the cool-down stage, and the locked in stresses are reorganized due to thermal contraction in the transverse direction.

Any modelling effort to predict the manufacturing distortions should include these mechanisms that are effective during the MRCC. The relative importance of various mechanisms can be found by a parametric study when the model is developed.

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